

Millifluidic valves and pumps made of tape and plastic

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Abstract

There is growing interest in producing micro- and milli-fluidic technologies made of thermoplastic with integrated fluidic control elements that are easy to assemble and suitable for mass production. Here, we developed millifluidic valves and pumps made of acrylic layers bonded with double-sided tape that are simple and fast to assemble. We demonstrate that a layer of pressure-sensitive adhesive (PSA) is flexible enough to be deformed at relatively low pressures. A chemical treatment deposited on specific regions of the PSA prevents it from sticking to the thermoplastic, which enabled us to create three different types of valves in normally open or closed configurations. We characterized different aspects of their performance, their operating pressures, the cut-off pressure values to open or close the valves (for different configurations and sizes), and the flow rate and volume pumped by seven different micropumps. As an application, we implemented a glucose assay with integrated pumps and valves, automatically generating glucose dilutions and reagent mixing. The ability to create polymeric microfluidic control units made with tape paves the way for their mass manufacturing.

Introduction

On-chip valves and micropumps are key components to control flow, automate assays, control the delivery of reagents and samples at defined time points, and increase throughput. While polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) enabled the emergence of highly functional on-chip microvalves and peristaltic pumps, it has several shortcomings¹⁻⁴, most upsetting is its difficulty to mass-produce devices made of this elastomer. PDMS fabrication protocols have not yet been transferable to standard industrialization techniques, such as injection molding or wafer-level production, that could drastically reduce the cost of a device^{5,6}.

Thermoplastic materials have gained significant popularity for microfluidic applications^{1,7} because they can be manufactured in large volumes at low cost by employing a set of replication and direct fabrication techniques, such as injection and compression molding, hot embossing, microthermoforming, casting, micro-milling, laser ablation, plasma etching and 3D printing⁸⁻¹³. Thermoplastics are economical, relatively resistant to chemicals, have excellent optical transparency, and possess different mechanical properties. Cyclic olefin copolymer (COC), polycarbonate (PC), poly (methyl methacrylate) (PMMA), polystyrene (PS), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polypropylene (PP), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), and cycloolefin copolymer (COC), among others^{7,14,15}, are some of the most common thermoplastics used in industry and also to manufacture microfluidic devices. Unfortunately, the assembly and bonding of layers of different materials (or even the same material) are often the most complex and time-consuming steps for efficient mass-production of microfluidic devices. Thus, industry, as well as academia, are increasingly interested in producing microtechnologies made of thermoplastic with integrated fluidic control elements that are easy to assemble and suitable for mass production^{15,16}.

One of the most popular microfluidic valve is the pressure-actuated valve¹⁷⁻¹⁹. This valve consists of a control and flow layer separated by a thin, flexible material —typically an elastomer. When the control channel is actuated, the membrane deforms and pinches off or opens the flow channel¹⁷⁻¹⁹. This architecture has inspired similar thermoplastic valves and pumps that use thin layers of elastomer or flexible membranes such as PDMS²⁰⁻²³, Viton²³, thermoplastic polyurethane^{14,24}, fluorinated ethylene–propylene Teflon²⁵⁻²⁷, and Fluorocur perfluoropolyether²⁸. Exceptionally, valves and pumps made of thin membranes of rigid materials such as PMMA¹⁸ or PP¹ have been also demonstrated.

While PDMS microvalves and other MEMS-based valves are typically fabricated in Class 6/7 cleanrooms using lithography tools, microfluidic devices and fluidic control elements with larger dimensions (>100 μm) can be prototyped in standard labs using digital fabrication tools (e.g. laser and milling engraving/cutting techniques^{14,18}, 3D printing^{29,30}) or injection molding, among others³¹. The advantage of these tools is that they are more practical, inexpensive, and can be used to either produce master molds for PDMS³² or to directly fabricate fully assembled and functional microfluidic devices with integrated valves and pumps. These tools will definitely decrease the cost to prototype microfluidic devices, but they are not ideal fabrication methods for mass producing them as it only allows to produce a few items at a time.

To achieve a strong bond between thermoplastics layers and/or membranes, typical bonding methods rely on either (i) physical surface modifications (e.g. UV or oxygen plasma exposure), (ii) chemical surface treatments (using chloroform, organic solvents, photocurable resins, adhesion promoters or liquid adhesives), or (iii) thermal fusion bonding (requiring high pressures, ~ 7 MPa, and high temperatures, 50 - 390°C)³³⁻³⁶. Most of these protocols can take anywhere from 4 to 24 h^{35,36} and need to be carefully optimized (sometimes a combination of chemical treatment, temperature, and pressure) to prevent sealing failures or unwanted deformations on the microchannels³⁵⁻³⁷.

Therefore, integrating valves and micropumps using simpler and universal methods for joining multilayer microfluidic thermoplastic devices that does not involve physical or chemical treatments is highly desirable, as it would reduce the time and cost of producing microfluidic devices. Pressure sensitive adhesives (PSA) films consist of a thermoplastic carrier coated —on one or both sides— with a nonreactive adhesive, that is activated by pressure³⁸. PSAs are made so they achieve a good seal with little pressure. Compared to conventional widely used bonding techniques, these PSA films allow the multilayer bonding of thermoplastic materials in a simple and fast manner. For example, to achieve optimal bonding using the thermal fusion assisted by chloroform, there is typically only one bonding attempt that must be made as quickly as possible before the chloroform treatment effect is lost; in contrast, bonding with PSA can be performed at room temperature with no time constraints, which makes it straightforward to extend the alignment method to multiple layers. Additionally, compared to conventional techniques which generally form irreversible unions, layers bonded by PSA can be relatively easy to separate, either by mechanical peeling or chemical dissolution of the adhesive, potentially rendering them reusable and easy to

clean/sterilize³⁹. While for most conventional techniques, the substrates should be as flat and clean as possible before bonding, PSA-assisted bonding makes it possible to bond layers with relatively rough surfaces (which are common after micro-milling processes)³⁵. In summary, multilayer bonding by PSA is a robust, easy, and reliable technique to join substrates of different materials.

Here, we show that millifluidic valves and micropumps can be produced in thermoplastics using double-sided tapes, the same adhesive films that are commonly used in industry to bond layers of plastics and other materials³⁸. We show that pressure sensitive adhesives (PSA), a special subset of these tapes, have enough elasticity to deform upon a slight pressure and thus occlude a microfluidic channel³⁸. In addition, some PSAs are biocompatible and transparent, ideal to be used in any type of biochemical assays and cell culture^{38,40}. We demonstrate the manufacture and operation of normally open or closed valves and seven micropump configurations; our valves can withstand high pressures of at least 207 kPa without any leakage. This type of fluidic control elements allows for a quick, practical, and versatile way to bond multiple fluidic layers avoiding complex protocols such as solvent or thermal bonding. Finally, we implemented a glucose detection assay in a device containing 8 chambers integrated with 16 peristaltic pumps of various pumping capacities and 16 valves, controlled with only 5 pneumatic control lines.

Materials and methods

Valve microfabrication. 1.3-mm thick PMMA sheets (ME303018, Goodfellow) were used to produce the valves and pumps using a milling machine (MDX-40A, Roland AG) with a spindle speed of 10,000 rpm and a feed rate of 1 mm/s. A 200 μm square end-mill (1600-0080L012, Kyocera) was used to carve out the microchannels and valve structures, while a 500 μm square end mill (1610-0200L060, Kyocera) was used to cut holes and individual microfluidic devices from a PMMA sheet. The flow channels for the donut valves were milled on both sides of the PMMA slabs.

The devices consist of at least two acrylic layers (control and flow layers) bonded by double-sided PSA. The geometry of flow layer for donut valves includes circular valves with 2.5 mm diameter, a ring structure in the center of the valve with 600 μm of inner diameter, 150 μm ring edge thickness and 200 μm of ring structure height for normally closed (NC) and 100 μm of ring structure height for normally open (NO) valve. For NC gate valve, four different

diameters (0.5, 1, 2, 3 mm) and three bar widths (200, 300, and 400 μm) were micromachined, **Fig. S1**.

After producing the flow and control layers, they are manually aligned and bonded with a transparent double-sided pressure sensitive adhesive (dPSA) (ARcare 92712, Adhesive Research). One of the protective liners of the dPSA is peeled off and the exposed adhesive layer bonded to the control layer. Next, the second protective liner is removed and a drop of clear nail varnish (Im nails, Cosmetobelleza natural im, Mexico) diluted in acetone at a 1:3 ratio is placed in regions overlapping the area of the valve. After drying for 10 min at ambient temperature, a thin nitrocellulose polymer layer is created on the PSA, passivating the adhesive layer. A washing step is not necessary highlighting the simplicity of our method. Volumes of 50, 200, 500, and 1500 nL are used for valves diameters of 1, 2, 3, and 4 mm, respectively. The composition of the nail varnish according to the manufacturer is: ethyl acetate, toluene, ethyl alcohol, acrylates copolymer, nitrocellulose, butyl acetate, toluene sulfonamide formaldehyde resin (TSF), dibutyl phthalate, butyl alcohol, D-panthenol, benzophenone¹. Afterwards, the flow layer is aligned and bonded to the control layer by applying pressure with a hand roller over the flow layer until a completely transparent layer is observed without bubbles, which guarantees an adequate seal between the acrylic layers. Finally, Tygon tubes (1.5 mm outer diameter, AAD04103, Saint Gobain) were glued (Loctite 495, Henkel) to the inlets and outlets of the chip for pneumatic control and fluid handling.

PSA layer deformation analysis. Valves with a diameter of 1, 2, 3, and 4 mm were fabricated without the seat structures (ring structure and transverse barrier) to allow the free displacement of the PSA layer. A 1% weight/volume (w/v) suspension of 4.8 μm fluorescent microparticles (Fluoro-Max, Thermo Fisher) was diluted 1:100 in distilled water. A drop of the microparticle suspension was placed on the valve area. Next, the liquid medium was evaporated at 70 °C for 10 min to allow the microparticles to sediment and attach on the PSA surface. Finally, acquisition of Z-stack image was performed using an inverted epifluorescence microscope (Axio Observer A1, Carl Zeiss).

Microvalve set-up and characterization. The valve control layer was connected to a module with four electro-pneumatic valves (MH1, Festo), which can switch between pressure and vacuum. A custom Python code running in a Raspberry PI was used to control the valves. An air compressor (EL200E400, Evans) with a manual regulator (11142NNKRSP, Fairchild) was used to set gauge pressures from 0 to 103.4 kPa as required. A vacuum pump (75R647-V101-H301X, GAST) was used to generate pressures

of ≈ -90 kPa. As a reliability test for our valves, we programmed a sequence of 50,000 cycles, and then we evaluated whether (i) delamination occurred by visual inspection on the edges of the device and assessed by the appearance of liquid or air pockets, (ii) air bubbles appearing between PSA and PMMA, which indicate sealing failures, (iii) PSA membrane integrity was compromised by applying pneumatic pressure in the control layer and determining if the air passed through the membrane into the flow layer.

To characterize the valve's open-to-closed transition, we applied a constant pressure between 0 and 103.4 kPa to the flow channel without applying pressure to the control layer. The flow rate generated for each pressure was recorded with a flowmeter (M Flow unit, Fluigent). Next, the pressure in the control layer was varied from 0 to 103.4 kPa in 3.5 kPa/s increments to close the valve. The shutoff pressure required to close the valve was determined when the flow rate in the flow layer reached 0 $\mu\text{L/s}$.

On the other hand, for the valve's closed-to-open transition, we applied a constant pressure to the control layer to keep the valve closed. Next, pressure in the flow channel (pressure-driven flow) varied from 0 to 103.4 kPa in 3.5 kPa/s increments. The pressure required to open the valve (opening pressure) was determined when the pressure-driven flow reached at least 1 $\mu\text{L/s}$.

Micropump characterization. The valves in each of the micropumps were actuated either at 103 kPa to close the valves or at -90 kPa to open them. The flow rate and volume pumped per cycle were measured by filling a tube (inner diameter, 0.508 mm) for a specific period or cycle. The maximum pump discharge pressure was determined by connecting a tube at the outlet of the pump, and with the air compressor setting pressures from 0 to 138 kPa as required, opposite to the direction of the pumped flow, and measured it with a manometer when the liquid flow at the outlet of the peristaltic pump stopped.

Glucose detection. An acrylic device that integrates valves, pumps, mixers, chambers, reservoirs, and a gradient generator was designed to perform eight detection assays of glucose simultaneously. The acrylic device included eight pear-shaped chambers, 16 valves and 16 peristaltic pumps of various pumping capacities, controlled with only 5 pneumatic control lines. Reagents and samples were dispensed by pipetting into the microfluidic device reservoirs.

A glucose detection kit (GAGO20, Sigma-Aldric) was dissolved in 9.8 mL of deionized water and stored at -20°C . A 10 mM Ampliflu Red solution (90101-5MG-F, Sigma-Aldrich) was

dissolved in DMSO (D2650-5X5ML, Sigma-Aldrich) and stored at 4°C. For the glucose detection assay, a mixture of 1 μ L of enzymatic solution and 1 μ L of Ampliflu Red solution was freshly prepared in 1 mL of PBS pH 7.4. A stock solution of 25 mM glucose (12491015, Thermo Fisher) was supplemented with FBS 10% v/v (16000-036, ThermoFisher) and Penicillin-streptomycin 1% v/v (15140-122, ThermoFisher).

The glucose detection assay was carried out in three stages: (i) glucose concentration gradient along the eight reaction chambers, (ii) enzymatic reaction and (iii) fluorescence detection. (i) First, a solution of 12 mM glucose and FITC (F7250-100, Sigma-Aldrich), (1 mg/ml, in a 1:1 ratio) was diluted in PBS (pH 7.4) using the gradient generator of the microfluidic device. (ii) Through reverse pumping (using only one pumping cycle and an activation time of 1.2 s) the enzyme solution composed of Horseradish peroxidase (HRP), Glucose oxidase (GOx), and Ampliflu Red, was dispensed into the pear-shaped chambers from the output reservoirs. Once the enzyme solution is injected into the reaction chambers, resorufin begins to be generated at a rate that depends on glucose concentration. Finally, fluorescence image of all chambers is acquired 15 minutes after the injection of the enzyme solution with an inverted epifluorescence microscope (Axio Observer A1, Carl Zeiss) to measure resorufin.

Results and discussion

Concept of the microfluidic valve using PSA. The adhesive property of dPSA is practical for bonding several layers of thermoplastics because it only requires removing the protective liners of the adhesive and applying pressure to activate the adhesive, **Fig. 1a, Fig. S2**. Additionally, the elasticity of PSA (Young's modulus, 3 - 3.8 GPa) provides enough flexibility to deflect upon applying pressure and, thus, is convenient for creating pressure actuated valves. We took advantage of these properties to create valves made only of thermoplastic and PSA.

The multilayer assembly process for each valve configuration is performed using dPSA, in which the liners that protect the adhesive layers are removed to bond them to a thermoplastic surface that has been previously machined with microchannels, **Fig. 1b-i**. However, the dPSA attaches irreversibly to a thermoplastic surface, which would prevent a valve from opening. Therefore, the dPSA surface that is in direct contact with the plastic surface of the valves needs to be passivated to remove its tackiness before bonding to another layer **Fig. S2**. We found that spotting a small volume of nail varnish dissolved in acetone on the dPSA is sufficient to passivate the dPSA surface, **Fig. 1b-ii**. This passivation

method is as simple as applying a drop of nail varnish and letting it dry for 10 min at ambient temperature conditions. The drop volume defines the treatment area. Typically, nail varnish is made of polymers such as nitrocellulose, p-toluenesulfonamide formaldehyde resin (TFS resin), and dibutyl phthalate, among others, that are dissolved in organic solvents such as butyl acetate, toluene or ethyl alcohol^{41,42}. These solvents have high volatility, which increases the higher their vapor pressure. During the PSA passivation step and under ambient conditions, we expected that acetone or ethyl alcohol (vapor pressure of 30.8 and 7.8 kPa at 25°C, respectively) would evaporate faster than toluene or butyl acetate (5.3 kPa and 1.2 kPa, respectively). After the solvents have evaporated, nitrocellulose polymerizes

a Double-layer Pressure Sensitive Adhesive (dPSA)

b

i. Release liners and align to microfluidic control layer

ii. Apply blocking solution and let it dry

iii. Align and bond to microfluidic flow layer

Figure 1. Fabrication of millifluidic valves made of tape. **a**) Schematic of the double-layer Pressure Sensitive Adhesive (dPSA) layers. **b**) Assembling the millifluidic valves involves releasing the dPSA liners and bonding one side to the microfluidic control layer (i). Next, nail varnish is applied on the opposite side of the dPSA and is left to evaporate for a few min (ii). The micrographs showed a droplet of nail varnish before and after solvent evaporation. Note that we have intentionally extended the blocking area outside the valve to visualize better the nitrocellulose layer left after the solvent evaporates. The dried spot prevents the dPSA from sticking to any plastic structure that encounters it. The flow layer is aligned and bonded to the control layer to create a millifluidic valve (iii). Applying vacuum on the control layer deflects down the dPSA and opens the valve.

and forms a uniform film on the surface, **Fig. 1b-ii, iii**. The dibutyl phthalate and TSF resin will most likely make the nitrocellulose film more flexible, durable, and allow them to strongly adhere to the PSA ⁴¹.

In general, our devices consist of at least two acrylic layers bonded by dPSA. Each acrylic layer contains a network of micromilled channels, in which one layer serves as a control layer to actuate the microvalves, while the other layer contains the fluidic channels. One of the layers containing the valve structure is aligned to the spotted solution, forming a microfluidic valve, **Fig.1b-iii**. The thin transparent layer of nail varnish prevents the PSA from sticking to the valves while the flexibility allows it to deform when applying pressure to one of the microfluidic layers. We designed three different types of valves: a normally closed (NC) gate valve, and a NC and normally open (NO) donut valve. The valves can open or close continually and reliably for at least for 50,000 cycles. We optimized the nail varnish-acetone solution to prevent dissolving the PSA or to form any thick residues. Additionally, our valve technology can withstand pressures of at least 207 kPa (maximum pressure of our pressure regulator) without delaminating. Therefore, these dPSA films can be used as a versatile material to join multiple layers of thermoplastic materials and, in turn, be used as a flexible membrane to actuate valves in a simple and fast manner compared to conventional methods.

PSA layer deflection analysis. Before designing our millifluidic valves, we characterized how much the dPSA layer deflects under different pressures. Two microfluidic circular structures were bonded with dPSA and subjected to a uniform load (7 - 207 kPa) from one side, **Fig. 2a**. To visualize the dPSA layer deformation, we sprinkled fluorescence microbeads on the top surface of the PSA layer, **Fig. 2b**. As expected, the circular PSA layer undergoes a parabolic deformation when actuated, reaching a maximum deflection at the center of the layer, **Fig. 2b**. The height of the parabola vertex increases with both the applied pressure and the diameter of the dPSA layer, reaching almost 300 μm for a 4-mm diameter structure at 207 kPa, **Fig. 2c**.

We estimated the dPSA deflection height (δ) using **Eq. 1** when applying a pressure (P) at the center of a thin circular layer of thickness (h) of a material with a Young's modulus (E) and a Poisson's ratio (σ) ^{29,43}.

$$\frac{PR^4}{Eh^4} = \frac{5.33}{1 - \sigma^2} * \frac{\delta}{h} + \frac{2.6}{1 - \sigma^2} * \left(\frac{\delta}{h}\right)^3 \quad (1)$$

The dPSA layer consists of a 13- μm thick PET carrier sandwiched by two 18- μm thick adhesive layers. The Young's modulus of PET (2.76 GPa) is three orders of magnitude larger than the one of the adhesive layers (0.47 MPa), and thus their contribution to the overall dPSA layer Young's modulus can be deemed negligible. Likewise, the thin film of nitrocellulose and TSF resin has not been considered for these calculations since its thickness is in the micrometer range ($\sim 1\text{-}10\ \mu\text{m}$) and do not change its overall mechanical properties. We therefore use the properties of PET in our calculations, using a Poisson's ratio of 0.3 and a thickness of 13 μm . **Fig. 2c** shows that indeed the experimental data and our analytical estimation (dashed lines) are very similar.

Noteworthy, **Eq. 1** and **Fig. 2c** show that the relation between applied pressure and the deformation of the membrane has a strong dependence on the membrane's radius R: it is more difficult to deform a relatively small membrane than large ones. This finding has important consequences on how valves of different sizes perform, as will be discussed in the next sections.

Figure 2. Characterization of PSA layer deflection. **a)** Schematic of the dPSA layer deflection height analysis. Blue arrows represent a variable pneumatic pressure applied onto the dPSA layer (green) covered with 4 μm fluorescent microparticles (yellow). **b)** Fluorescence microscopy analysis of the dPSA layer deflection as a function of pneumatic pressure. **c)** Summary experimental data of the PSA layer deflection height (μm) of four different valve sizes as a function of pneumatic pressure (continuous line) and analytical estimation of PSA deflection (dashed lines). Scale bars: 200 μm . SD error bars with 95 % confidence interval by triplicate (true replicates).

Normally Closed Gate Valve. The NC gate valve (GV) consists of a control layer and a flow layer, each layer engraved with microchannels on one side and bonded by dPSA, **Fig. S3**. The flow layer contains a bar that overlaps with the top control channel, **Fig. 3a**. Applying negative pressure on the control layer deforms the PSA layer upwards, opening the valve and allowing the flow of liquid from one side to the other side of the bottom flow channel, **Fig. 3a, b**.

We tested a set of valves of four different diameters (0.5, 1, 2, and 3 mm) and three barrier widths (200, 300, and 400 μm), **Fig. 3c**. We firstly evaluated the effect of the valve diameter and the barrier width on the shutoff pressure. We performed exploratory experiments with a small set of diameters to determine preliminary trends and we considered that the best sizes for valves were 0.5 and 1 mm due to their low dead volume. Therefore, a more rigorous

Figure 3. Characterization of gate valves. **a)** Schematic of closed and open gate valves. Bottom row shows micrographs of both valves with flow and control layers filled with blue and red color dyes, respectively. **b)** Top image shows a cross-sectional view of a gate valve. The bottom micrograph highlights the gate valve bar; the roughness of the barrier due to micromilling can be appreciated. **c)** Plot shows the pressure required to close the valve (shutoff pressure) for different barrier widths and valve diameters, no significance (ns) by Kruskal-Wallis test, $P < 0.05$. **d)** Plot shows the pressure required to close the valve (shutoff pressure) at different pressure-driven flows for different valve diameters. **e)** Plot shows the fluid pressure required to open the valve (opening pressure) for different pneumatic closing pressures and different valve diameters. Scale bars: 0.5 mm, SEM error bars with 95 % confidence interval by triplicate (true replicates) and only one replicate for the 2,3 mm valves in Fig. 3e.

statistical study was carried out for these two valves. Nevertheless, the 2- and 3-mm valves are useful when integrated into a pump configuration and are included in the graphs. However, we performed a more rigorous statistical characterization for these larger valves in the pumps section. The shutoff pressure is the pneumatic pressure required in the control layer to close the valve starting from an initial state where the valve is open when a constant pressure-driven flow is applied to the flow layer. **Fig. 3c** shows that —within experimental variability, using a Kruskal-Wallis test, $P < 0.05$, the barrier width does not influence the valve closing.

In contrast, the pressure needed to close the valves is higher for the bigger valves (diameters of 2- and 3-mm) than for the smaller valves (diameters 0.5 and 1 mm). This figure only shows the experiments corresponding to a constant pressure of 6.7 kPa applied to the flow layer, but similar results were obtained at 34.5 kPa and 69 kPa conditions, **Fig. S4, S5**.

The fact that smaller valves are easier to close than bigger valves is expected because, relatively, a smaller membrane is harder to deflect than a bigger one, and the rigidity of the membrane helps to close the valve by pushing the membrane against the barrier. If a membrane of radius R is deflected a distance δ by a force f applied on the center of the membrane, the relation between the force and the deflection distance is $f = 16\pi D\delta/R^2$, where the flexural rigidity $D = Eh^3/12(1-\sigma^2)$, with E being the Young's modulus, σ is Poisson's ratio, and h is membrane's thickness⁴⁴. The force f varies as a function of membrane's radius R to the power of -2. Therefore, for a given displacement δ , the force will be much larger for small membranes than for large ones. This deflection would be associated with a force f of the membrane against the seat structure (transverse barrier). We estimate that this force is approximately ten times larger for a 0.5-mm membrane than for a 3-mm membrane, while the forces of 2- and 3-mm membranes are almost equal. This is consistent with the behavior of the shutoff pressure we observed, similar for 2- and 3-mm valves but smaller for 0.5- and 1-mm valves, **Fig. 3c**.

Another indication of the large rigidity of the small valves is that it increases the resistance to flow. Consider an initial state in which the valve is relaxed with no extra pressure applied to the control layer. If a constant pressure is applied to the flow channel, the liquid pushes the PSA layer upward, opening the valve. Under these circumstances, the opening of the valve depends only on the deformation of the PSA layer caused by the liquid flowing, **Fig. S6a**. Membrane deflection depends on its flexural rigidity D and on membrane's size^{43,45,46}. The smaller the PSA membrane the closer it is to its anchor points (i.e., the rigid edges

where the PSA is sandwiched by the acrylic layers) and thus the higher its resistance to being deformed by the fluid, **Fig. S6b**. Consequently, the PSA deformation height (δ) will be smaller for 0.5- and 1-mm than for 2- and 3-mm valves.

The characterization of the pneumatic pressure in the control layer required to close the gate valve from an initial state where the valve is opened while sustaining a constant pressure driven flow is shown in **Fig. 3d**. In general, these results confirm that small valves close more readily than the large ones, and that 2- and 3-mm valves require the same pressure to close them. Interestingly, the shutoff pressure is a linear function of the applied flow pressure (slope=1). For the 0.5-mm valve the shutoff pressure is equal to the flow pressure, while larger valves require higher shutoff pressures for the same flow pressure. This behavior is expected because the PSA area, where the pneumatic pressure is exerted (in the control layer) and the area where the flow exerts pressure on the PSA layer, are the same. Therefore, it is only necessary for the pneumatic pressure to overcome the pressure in the fluidic channel so that the PSA layer can be in contact with the barrier structure. However, the pressure needed to close the large valves is almost four times the pressure on the other side of the membrane. This implies that a considerable force is needed to press the membrane against the barrier to close the valve. For the 0.5-mm valve, this extra force comes from its high rigidity due to its small size as discussed before. Higher pressures are required to seal the valves presumably because of the irregularities on the barrier's surface created during the fabrication process ^{47,48}. A different fabrication method (e.g., mold injection, or polishing the surfaces by exposing them to chloroform after milling) should improve the sealing of the valves. The typical roughness of a surface in thermoplastics after micromilling is between 100 and 200 nm but it can be reduced to 15 nm by using chloroform ⁴⁸. This roughness is typically larger around the edges ⁴⁷. A photograph of the border of the barrier of one of our devices is shown in **Fig. 3b**.

Fig. 3e shows the characterization of the flow pressure required to open the gate valve from an initial state where there is a constant pneumatic pressure applied in the control layer. We observed that the flow pressure required to open a closed valve is approximately twice the pressure applied on the control layer. In this case, the flow pressure only exerts a force in one side of the valve (i.e., half of the total valve area) because the barrier structure divides the valve into two halves, while in the control layer the air pressure actuates over the whole area of the PSA membrane. The force on the membrane is the pressure times the area, thus the flow pressure must double the pneumatic pressure to equalize the forces. This behavior

is consistent with the results shown in **Fig. 3e** for 0.5, 1 and 2-mm valve diameters, but not for 3-mm valve diameter because it seems to require more than twice the pressure in the flow channel to overcome the pneumatic pressure in the control layer. However, for the case of 0.5- and 1-mm membranes in close to open transition, there doesn't seem to be any effect of membrane size on the opening transition, and it is only necessary twice the pressure in the flow layer with respect to the pressure in the control layer in order to open the valve.

Donut Valve. In contrast to the gate valve, the donut valve can be configured as a NC or NO valve, **Fig 4a-c and S1**. The donut valve consists of three acrylic layers bonded by two layers of PSA, **Fig. S3**. The control layer has channels engraved on one side. Microchannels are engraved on both sides of the flow layer, and one side features a ring structure in the center of a circular pool. The height of the ring structure defines the configuration of the valve, either a NC valve (when the ring structure is in contact with the PSA), **Fig. 4a**, or a NO valve (when there is a 100- μm gap between the PSA and the ring structure), **Fig. 4b**.

Figure 4. Characterization of donut valves. **a, b)** Lateral view of schematics and micrographs of the normally closed (NC) and normally open (NO) donut valve, respectively. The NC valves require that the pressure in the control layer P_c be greater than the pressure in the flow layer P_f to stop the liquid to advance inside the channel. Orange arrows point to the gap. **c)** Top view micrographs of a donut valve closed and open (left and right). Color red and blue indicate the control and flow layers, respectively. **d)** Plot shows the pneumatic pressure required to close the valve against different pressure-driven flows for NC and NO donut-type valves. **e)** Plot shows the flow pressure required (opening pressure) to open the NC and NO donut-type valve as a function of pneumatic pressures in the control layer. Scale bars: 0.5 mm, SEM error bars with 95 % confidence interval by triplicate (true replicates).

The central hole in the pool allows liquid to flow from the bottom side of the flow layer to the upper side. A third thin PMMA layer is used to seal the bottom flow channel.

In contrast to other type of NC valves that remain in a closed state when no pressure is applied in the control line ^{49,50}, our NC donut valve does require a sustained pneumatic pressure in the control layer to keep it closed when there is liquid flowing through the flow layer. The pressure applied to the control layer should be higher than the liquid pressure. Although the ring structure is in contact with the PSA, the high pressure in the control layer ensures a proper seal which keeps the valve closed. On the other hand, applying negative pressure on the control layer of an NC donut valve deforms the PSA layer upwards, opening the valve, and allowing the flow of liquid through the ring structure. In the case of a NO donut valve, the PSA deforms downwards when positive pressure is applied, closing the hole of the ring structure and blocking liquid flow to the upper side of the flow layer. The size of this gap must be within the deflection capacity of the PSA layer to close the valve.

Fig. 4d shows the shutoff pressure required to close a 2.5-mm NC and NO Donut type valves at increasing pressure in the flow channel. The shutoff pressure for the NC Donut valve as a function of the pressure on the flow channel behaves similarly to the NC Gate valve, **Fig. 3d**. Moreover, the size of the PSA membrane for the NC Donut valve is 2.5 mm, and the shutoff pressure is almost identical to the NC Gate valve with a similar size (2 mm). This behavior is expected because it is only necessary to overcome the pressure in the fluidic channel so that the PSA layer can be in contact with the donut structure. Additionally, both the gate and donut valves require an extra force (pneumatic pressure) to properly seal the valves, this is because the surface irregularities present in both valves due to milling process. The shutoff pressure required to close the valve against different pressures in the flow channel for the NO Donut valve is also a linear function (slope= 1) but displaced to higher shutoff pressures (about 27.6 kPa). An interesting conclusion of this set of characterization experiments is that it should be possible to control an array of NC and NO valves with different sizes from one control line operating at a single pressure.

Close-to-open transitions for NC and NO donut valves are shown in **Fig. 4e**. The pressure on the flow layer required to open the valve (opening pressure) as a function of the pneumatic pressure on the control layer for the NC donut valve is similar to the opening pressure of the 1-mm NC Gate valve. This is a surprising result because, together with the results of the opening pressure for the Gate valves **Fig. 3e**, it seems that the opening pressure is the same for all the valves studied here. This result suggests that the closed-to-

open transition is a complicated mechanism in which the fluid in the flow layer pushes against the seal between the membrane and the barrier, looking for somewhere to pass through. Since the seal between the membrane and the barrier results from the interaction between the varnish layer and the barrier surface that has irregularities due to machining, it can be thought that as the pressure in the flow layer increases, the fluid advances through the barrier seal until it percolates to the other side of the barrier and makes it past the other side of the valve. This percolation would occur locally along the valve seal, so it is not valve-type dependent. This scenario is supported by the curves of flow rate as a function of the pressure in the flow channel for the closed-to-open transition shown in **Fig. S7**, where the opening dynamics has two regimes: a slow flow increase followed by an abrupt opening, suggesting a local percolation behavior.

The opening pressure as a function of pneumatic pressure on the control layer for the NO Donut valve in **Fig. 4e** is a linear relation with the same slope as the NC Donut valve but it is displaced to lower opening pressures because a pneumatic pressure of 27.6 kPa is required to deflect the membrane enough to reach the donut structure and close the valve. This constant pressure is consistent with the constant pressure of 27.6 kPa that the shutoff pressure for the NO Donut valve is displaced upwards in **Fig. 4d**.

A large variability was observed for NO Donut valves curves in open-to-close and close-to-open transition, which could be explained by the surface imperfections generated after micromilling process over donut structure to generate a gap of 100 μm between donut structure and PSA layer. These surface imperfections could affect a proper sealing between the PSA layer and ring structure.

Micropump characterization. We designed and fabricated two types of micropumps. The micropumps consist of a pumping chamber that is either flanked by NC gate valves (μPGates , **Fig. 5a**) or NC donut valves (μPDonut , **Fig. 5b**). We characterized six μPGates with different pump capacities (types A to F) and one μPDonut (type G, the limitations of our fabrication method prevented from further miniaturization). The diameters of the valves or pump chambers for each pump type are shown in their respective figures.

The actuation sequence of these micropumps consists of cycles of six steps: 111, 011, 001, 101, 100, 110, where the first and last digit correspond to the state of the valves and the middle digit to the state of the pumping chamber. Numbers 1 and 0 represent either a closed or open state, respectively, **Fig. 5c**. The flow rate and the volume pumped per cycle depend

Figure 5. Characterization of two types of micropumps. Schematics show the design of the micropumps based on (a) the normally closed (NC) valves, μ PGates, or (b) on the NC donut valves, μ PDonut. Each pump consists of an input valve (VI), an output valve (VO) and a middle pumping chamber (PM). Dimensions of the diameters of the VI, VO, and PM pumps tested and characterized are shown in their respective panel. Scale bar: 1 mm. (c) Micrographs show the actuation sequence of a pump, where 1 and 0 represent either a closed or open valve, respectively. Scale bars: 0.5 mm. Plots show the volume pumped (d) and the flow rate (e) generated by each micropump for different frequencies. (f) Plot shows the range of flow rates that the different micropumps can generate. SEM error bars with 95 % confidence interval by triplicate (true replicates).

on the deflection of the pumping chamber membrane. Importantly, the actuation of this membrane is limited by the maximum actuation velocity of the electro-pneumatic valves (50 ms). **Fig. 5d, e** and **Fig. S8, S9** show the volumes and flow rates, respectively, generated by each type of pump as a function of the actuation frequency (cycle/s or Hz). The pumps generate flow rates ranging from ~ 2 nL/s to ~ 6 μ L/s. While our pumps achieved a wide range of pumped volumes, from as low as ~ 8 nL up to ~ 2.6 μ L per cycle —i.e., 3 orders of magnitude in dynamic range—, they operate steadily in the range of 40 nL to 3 μ L per cycle (type A: ~ 40 nL; B and C: ~ 330 nL; D, E and G: 1.4 μ L; F: ~ 2.6 μ L). Pumps D, E, and G (pumping membrane diameter of 3 mm) generate almost identical pump rates, as well as pumps B and C (pumping membrane diameter of 2 mm), implying that the size of the pumping chamber has the highest effect on the pumping efficiency irrespective of the dimensions of the side valves. In general, the pumps with the largest pumping chambers generated higher flow rates than pumps with smaller features.

All our pumps can pump a stable and constant volume per cycle up to frequencies below of ~3 Hz, after which the pumping performance starts to decrease, generating less volume pumped per cycle with a quick decline in flow rate. The equivalent period of this frequency for one step in the cycle is ~50 ms, which is the response time of the membrane to return to its original state. Lower actuation times do not allow for a complete closing and opening, thus decreasing the pump rate and reducing their performance (as judged by the large error bars). **Fig. 5f** condenses the flow rates produced by each pump type. In summary, adjusting the actuation times or dimensions of the pumping membrane leads to different flow rates that could lead to three orders of magnitude in difference.

We also characterized the pump discharge pressure, which is a measure of the maximum pressure that a pump can generate⁵¹. We determined directly the maximum pressure generated at the outlet of each pump (discharge pressure) by applying a opposite flow pressure in the outlet of each peristaltic pump tested. **Table S1** shows the discharge pressure for each pump. Notably, the maximum discharge pressures generated by our pumps range from ~62 to ~110.3 kPa, 3 times higher than other peristaltic micropumps that reported values of 34.5 kPa or much less^{52–54}.

Glucose detection. Finally, to showcase our technology we implemented a semi-automated glucose assay operated to run eight assays in parallel with a small footprint (4 x 5 cm), **Fig. 6a**. The device contains eight pear-shaped reaction chambers (each of ~1.13 μ L) where glucose assays are carried out. The control elements for each reaction chamber are connected serially, thus requiring only five control lines to operate the whole device. The reaction chamber also works as a pump to mix solutes and solvents delivered through two micropumps. To generate an on-chip dilution curve, we kept the same dimensions of the micropumps to the left of each reaction chamber (1 mm diam), while the dimensions of the micropumps on the right side were adjusted to pump different volumes per cycle of the solvent, **Fig. 6b**. The diameter (and thus the volume) of these latter micropumps was estimated by relating the pumped volume per cycle as a function of the pumping chamber's size (**Fig. S10** and **Table S2**). Using this architecture, we were able to create an exponential gradient generator optimized for a fixed range of dilutions (1:1, 1:2 1:4, 1:8, 1:16 and 1:32).

Effective mixing in the reaction chambers is achieved by actuating the chamber and the flanking valves every 2.5 s for two min, **Fig. 6c**. Active mixing works because, although the size of our structures favors low Reynolds numbers, the transitions from high-to-low and low-to-high pressures in the control layer are very fast—in the order of tenths of

Figure 6. Implementation of a semi-automated glucose assay. **a)** Exploded view of the glucose detection device. **b)** Design of the glucose detection device with eight reaction chambers, sixteen micropumps, and eight output valves. The active mixers comprise the reaction chamber and its flanking valves. **c)** Schematic of the operation of the active mixer. **d)** Photographs of a microfluidic device filled initially with color dyes (left) and after 2 min of active mixing. Dilutions are labeled in red color. **e)** Plots show the dilution curve of Rhodamine obtained by conventional pipetting and on the chip, SEM error bars with 95 % confidence interval by triplicate (pseudo replicates). **f)** Fluorescence images of different dilutions of Glucose-FITC and of resorufin after incubation with the HRP-GOx-Ampliflu-Red reagent. **g)** Plot shows the on-chip detection of different concentrations of glucose. M.F.I (a.u.): Mean Fluorescence Intensity (arbitrary units), SD error bars with 95 % confidence interval by triplicate (pseudo replicates).

milliseconds. Therefore, the PSA membranes move violently, creating fast flows within the channels and through the valves. We estimated that the Reynolds number in our system during pumping can be as high as 50, which is enough to generate mixing using periodic cycling. **Fig. 6d** shows photographs of the on-chip generated dilutions after two minutes of

active mixing (right), confirming that indeed a homogenous mixing is possible in each chamber. We corroborated the performance of our microfluidic gradient generator by comparing a dilution curve of Rhodamine B created on-chip and off-chip (conventional pipetting). The data shows no significant difference between the two curves, **Fig. 6e**.

Next, we created on-chip calibration curves of glucose-FITC at different concentrations with an initial stock solution of 6mM (1:1, 1:2, 1:4, 1:8, 1:16, and 1:32, top row **Fig. 6f**). Then, the enzyme solution (composed of HRP, GOx, and Ampliflu Red) was introduced through the outlet into the pear-shaped reaction chambers. 15 minutes after the injection of this solution (bottom row **Fig. 6f**), resorufin was quantitated, **Fig. 6g**. We determined a limit of detection (LOD) of 0.2142 mM and a detection range of 0.375 mM to 6 mM. Our results suggest that is possible to detect hypoglycemia and values close to hyperglycemia, used in the diagnosis of prediabetes⁵⁵. Furthermore, the gradient generator demonstrates that we can implement pumps of different flow rates, maintaining common control lines and the number of operating cycles constant for all pumps.

Conclusions

PSAs are typically used to prototype polymer microfluidic devices with a fast turnaround time. A layer of PSA is typically cut through with a laser cutter or a craft cutter. These cuts in the PSA define the width of the microfluidic channels, while its thickness defines the channels' height. The PSA layer is then sandwiched between two layers of thermoplastics. However, the more intricate the design of the channel network, the more difficult is to handle the PSA layer because PSA is very thin and flexible, but also because the cuts tend to stick together or get entangled after removing the liners. Aligning layers of PSA and thermoplastics then becomes a difficult step to automate.

Moreover, craft cutters use a sharp knife that limits the cuts to widths $> 200 \mu\text{m}$ ⁵⁶. While laser cutters can produce cuts as small as $25 \mu\text{m}$ wide, high-resolution lasers are commonly expensive ($>30,000$ USD) and generate burnt edges and rough surfaces⁵⁷. In contrast, our manufacturing and assembling approach overcomes these difficulties by not cutting the PSA layer but rather bonding the intact PSA layer over the plastic layer either manually or using laminators. This approach also opens other possibilities to increase the channel's resolution because the microfluidic channels can now be milled, embossed directly or injection molded¹³.

In this paper, we engineered millifluidic valves and pumps composed of micro-milled thermoplastic layers joined with tape. Our simple design uses the PSA as a versatile material to join the layers and to actuate the control elements. This method allows us to design and characterize three types of valves in different sizes and seven configurations of pumps. We tested valves of 0.5, 1, 2, and 3 mm in diameter demonstrating reliability to the control of fluid at different pressures with no leakage. We were able to make valves as small as 0.5 mm, comparable to the size of the fluidic channel and thus minimizing the dead volume. In addition, the pumps produced flow rates in a range from 2 nL/s to 6 μ L/s with discharge pressures up to 110.3 kPa depending in its size and configuration. Overall, we presented a suite of valves and pumps in a wide range of flow control capacities that will make possible the design of microfluidic devices for broad biomedical applications ⁵⁸.

We also demonstrated a functional microfluidic device that integrates valves, pumps, mixers, detection chambers, reagent reservoirs, and a gradient generator to quantitate glucose with a fluorescence assay. The device only used 5 control lines because we designed pumps of specific flow-rate capacities to achieve the desired concentrations. With this example, we demonstrated the integration of several flow control elements in two micro-milled acrylic layers bonded by PSA.

Importantly, the valves and pumps presented here are suitable for mass production techniques because their assembly does not require complex treatments such as physical or chemical surface modifications, or thermal fusion bonding. Although we use micro-milling to produce the microfluidic channels in acrylic, these layers could be mass manufactured by hot embossing, micro-injection or thermal formation. While we used high-quality and medical-grade acrylic and PSA to produce our devices and results in a total cost of \$2.2 USD per device, this cost could be greatly reduced by purchasing the materials in bulk. As we mentioned before, because the PSA is not cut through, machines like laminators can be used to automate the bonding process. Thus, we believe our technique is suitable for mass manufacturing and the device's final cost could potentially be less than \$1 USD.

One disadvantage of our technique is the passivation step necessary to eliminate the tackiness on the valve area; however, an automated droplet spotter could be used to facilitate this process. In general, our new technology simplifies the assembly of microfluidic devices bonded by PSA and paves the way to mass manufacture microfluidics devices with integrated valves and pumps.

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Conflicts of interest

J.L.G-C is an employee of Hoffmann-La Roche AG.

References

- 1 W. Jung, M. J. Uddin, K. Namkoong, W. Chung, J. H. Kim and J. S. Shim, *RSC Adv.*, 2020, **10**, 28390–28396.
- 2 J. N. Lee, C. Park and G. M. Whitesides, *Anal. Chem.*, 2003, **75**, 6544–6554.
- 3 I. E. Araci and S. R. Quake, *Lab Chip*, 2012, **12**, 2803–2806.
- 4 J. L. Garcia-Cordero and S. J. Maerkl, *Lab Chip*, 2014, **14**, 2642–2650.
- 5 A. Folch, *Introduction to BioMEMS*, CRC Press, 2016.
- 6 I. E. Araci and P. Brisk, *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.*, 2014, **25**, 60–68.
- 7 K. M. Weerakoon-Ratnayake, C. E. O'Neil, F. I. Uba and S. A. Soper, *Lab Chip*, 2017, **17**, 362–381.
- 8 H. Becker and C. Gärtner, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2008, **390**, 89–111.
- 9 N. Bhattacharjee, A. Urrios, S. Kang and A. Folch, *Lab Chip*, 2016, **16**, 1720–1742.
- 10 A. K. Au, H. Lai, B. R. Utela and A. Folch, *Microvalves and micropumps for BioMEMS*, 2011, vol. 2.
- 11 A. De Mello, *Lab Chip*, 2002, **2**, 31–36.
- 12 M. Focke, D. Kosse, C. Müller, H. Reinecke, R. Zengerle and F. Von Stetten, *Lab Chip*, 2010, **10**, 1365–1386.
- 13 P. E. Guevara-Pantoja, O. G. Chavez-Pineda, A. M. Solis-Serrano, J. L. Garcia-Cordero and G. A. Caballero-Robledo, *Lab Chip*, 2020, **20**, 3179–3186.
- 14 S. A. M. Shaegh, A. Pourmand, M. Nabavinia, H. Avci, A. Tamayol, P. Mostafalu, H.

- B. Ghavifekr, E. N. Aghdam, M. R. Dokmeci, A. Khademhosseini and Y. S. Zhang, *Sensors Actuators, B Chem.*, 2018, **255**, 100–109.
- 15 E. K. Sackmann, A. L. Fulton and D. J. Beebe, *Nature*, 2014, **507**, 181–189.
- 16 S. Battat, D. A. Weitz and G. M. Whitesides, *Lab Chip*, 2022, **22**, 530–536.
- 17 S. R. Quake, *Science*, 2002, **298**, 580–584.
- 18 P. E. Guevara-Pantoja, R. J. Jiménez-Valdés, J. L. García-Cordero and G. A. Caballero-Robledo, *Lab Chip*, 2018, **18**, 662–669.
- 19 E. P. Kartalov, A. Scherer, S. R. Quake, C. R. Taylor and W. F. Anderson, *J. Appl. Phys.*, 2007, **101**, 64505.
- 20 J. Y. Back, J. Y. Park, J. Il Ju, T. S. Lee and S. H. Lee, *J. Micromechanics Microengineering*, 2005, **15**, 1015–1020.
- 21 A. R. Norouzi, A. Nikfarjam and H. Hajghassem, *Microsyst. Technol.*, 2018, **24**, 2727–2736.
- 22 A. G. G. Toh, Z. F. Wang and S. H. Ng, in *2008 Symposium on Design, Test, Integration and Packaging of MEMS/MOEMS*, IEEE, 2008, pp. 267–272.
- 23 I. R. G. Ogilvie, V. J. Sieben, B. Cortese, M. C. Mowlem and H. Morgan, *Lab Chip*, 2011, **11**, 2455–2459.
- 24 P. Gu, T. Nishida and Z. H. Fan, *Electrophoresis*, 2014, **35**, 289–297.
- 25 P. A. Willis, B. D. Hunt, V. E. White, M. C. Lee, M. Ikeda, S. Bae, M. J. Pelletier and F. J. Grunthaler, *Lab Chip*, 2007, **7**, 1469–1474.
- 26 W. H. Grover, M. G. Von Muhlen and S. R. Manalis, *Lab Chip*, 2008, **8**, 913–918.
- 27 K. Ren, W. Dai, J. Zhou, J. Su and H. Wu, *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.*, 2011, **108**, 8162–8166.
- 28 P. A. Willis, F. Greer, M. C. Lee, J. A. Smith, V. E. White, F. J. Grunthaler, J. J. Sprague and J. P. Rolland, *Lab Chip*, 2008, **8**, 1024–1026.
- 29 A. K. Au, N. Bhattacharjee, L. F. Horowitz, T. C. Chang and A. Folch, *Lab Chip*, 2015, **15**, 1934–1941.

- 30 J. L. Sanchez Noriega, N. A. Chartrand, J. C. Valdoz, C. G. Cribbs, D. A. Jacobs, D. Poulson, M. S. Viglione, A. T. Woolley, P. M. Van Ry, K. A. Christensen and G. P. Nordin, *Nat. Commun.*, , DOI:10.1038/s41467-021-25788-w.
- 31 K. W. Oh and C. H. Ahn, *J. Micromechanics Microengineering*, , DOI:10.1088/0960-1317/16/5/R01.
- 32 E. G. B. M. Bossink, A. R. Vollertsen, J. T. Loessberg-Zahl, A. D. van der Meer, L. I. Segerink and M. Odijk, *Microsystems Nanoeng.*, , DOI:10.1038/s41378-022-00378-y.
- 33 H. Mekar, *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.*, 2017, **56**, 06GM04.
- 34 Z. Yin, L. Qi, H. Zou, L. Sun and S. Xu, *J. Micromechanics Microengineering*, 2015, **25**, 85015.
- 35 C. W. Tsao and D. L. DeVoe, *Microfluid. Nanofluidics*, 2009, 6, 1–16.
- 36 H. Becker and C. Gärtner, *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.*, 2008, **390**, 89–111.
- 37 L. Brown, T. Koerner, J. H. Horton and R. D. Oleschuk, *Lab Chip*, 2006, **6**, 66–73.
- 38 Z. Czech and A. Kowalczyk, in *Adhesives: Types, Mechanics and Applications*, 2011, pp. 466–529.
- 39 M. Serra, I. Pereiro, A. Yamada, J. L. Viovy, S. Descroix and D. Ferraro, *Lab Chip*, 2017, **17**, 629–634.
- 40 S. R. A. Kratz, C. Eilenberger, P. Schuller, B. Bachmann, S. Spitz, P. Ertl and M. Rothbauer, *Sci. Rep.*, 2019, **9**, 1–12.
- 41 R. Baran and H. I. Maibach, *Textbook of Cosmetic Dermatology*, 1998.
- 42 R. Baran, S. Goettmann and J. André, *Ann. Dermatol. Venereol.*, 2016, **143**, 389–396.
- 43 Y. S. Lee, N. Bhattacharjee and A. Folch, *Lab Chip*, 2018, **18**, 1207–1214.
- 44 LANDAU L. D. and LIFSHITZ E. M., in *Theory of Elasticity*, Elsevier, 1986, p. iii.
- 45 W. Inman, K. Domansky, J. Serdy, B. Owens, D. Trumper and L. G. Griffith, *J. Micromechanics Microengineering*, 2007, **17**, 891–899.

- 46 D. C. Leslie, C. J. Easley, E. Seker, J. M. Karlinsey, M. Utz, M. R. Begley and J. P. Landers, *Nat. Phys.*, 2009, **5**, 231–235.
- 47 R. Hernandez-Perez, J. L. García-Cordero and J. V. Escobar, *Phys. Rev. E*, 2017, **96**, 1–13.
- 48 I. R. G. Ogilvie, V. J. Sieben, C. F. A. Floquet, R. Zmijan, M. C. Mowlem and H. Morgan, *J. Micromechanics Microengineering*, 2010, **20**, 065016.
- 49 B. Mosadegh, H. Tavana, S. C. Lesher-Perez and S. Takayama, *Lab Chip*, 2011, **11**, 738–742.
- 50 A. Pourmand, S. A. M. Shaegh, H. B. Ghavifekr, E. Najafi Aghdam, M. R. Dokmeci, A. Khademhosseini and Y. S. Zhang, *Fabrication of whole-thermoplastic normally closed microvalve, micro check valve, and micropump*, Elsevier B.V., 2018, vol. 262.
- 51 S. Mohith, P. N. Karanth and S. M. Kulkarni, *Mechatronics*, 2019, **60**, 34–55.
- 52 W. H. Grover, A. M. Skelley, C. N. Liu, E. T. Lagally and R. A. Mathies, *Sensors Actuators, B Chem.*, 2003, **89**, 315–323.
- 53 S. A. M. Shaegh, Z. Wang, S. H. Ng, R. Wu, H. T. Nguyen, L. C. Z. Chan, A. G. G. Toh and Z. Wang, *Microfluid. Nanofluidics*, 2015, **19**, 557–564.
- 54 W. Zhang, S. Lin, C. Wang, J. Hu, C. Li, Z. Zhuang, Y. Zhou, R. A. Mathies and C. J. Yang, *Lab Chip*, 2009, **9**, 3088–3094.
- 55 G. Cappon, M. Vettoretti, G. Sparacino and A. Facchinetti, *Diabetes Metab. J.*, 2019, **43**, 383–397.
- 56 P. K. Yuen and V. N. Goral, *Lab Chip*, 2010, **10**, 384–387.
- 57 L. E. Locascio, D. J. Ross, P. B. Howell and M. Gaitan, *Methods Mol. Biol.*, 2006, **339**, 37–46.
- 58 O. G. Chavez-Pineda, R. Rodriguez-Moncayo, D. F. Cedillo-Alcantar, P. E. Guevara-Pantoja, J. U. Amador-Hernandez and J. L. Garcia-Cordero, *Electrophoresis*, 2022, **43**, 1667–1700.